

On the Nature of Antimony Trichloride

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Manuscript received 3 July 1973; revised 1 July 1974; accepted 1 July 1974.

Antimony trichloride behaves as a fairly strong electrolyte in various aprotic solvents. In disulphuric acid it forms SbCl_2^+ ions while in fluorosulphuric and chlorosulphuric acids it gets solvolysed. Antimony trichloride forms two compounds of composition $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{SO}_3$ and $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{SO}_3$ with sulphur trioxide which are polymeric chlorosulphates. In the presence of strong donor molecules like triphenylchloromethane and pyridinium hydrochloride, antimony has a tendency to increase its co-ordination number to six. It also forms ionic compounds with organic tertiary bases, triphenylphosphine oxide and pyridine N-oxide.

Trihalides of phosphorus¹, arsenic^{2,3}, antimony^{4,5} and bismuth⁶ have been investigated as non-aqueous solvents and acid-base neutralisation reactions have been carried out in their liquid states to support their autoionisation as $2\text{MX}_3 \rightleftharpoons \text{MX}_3^+ + \text{MX}_3^-$. Antimony trichloride has been used as a Lewis acid in various non-aqueous solvents where it acts as a chloride ion acceptor molecule^{7,8} to form SbCl_4^- , SbCl_5^- and SbCl_6^- . A large number of addition compounds mainly with 1:1 ratio have been reported with hydrocarbons and organic halogen, oxygen and sulphur containing compounds⁹. Solubility of proteins and components of nucleic acids in antimony trichloride is useful in the study of their NH and OH i. r. absorption¹⁰. Some cryoscopic and conductance studies of the chlorides of alkali metals and quaternary ammonium salts have revealed some interesting results^{4, 11}. In the present studies, a number of compounds have been isolated which may be helpful to understand the nature of antimony trichloride.

Experimental :

Nitrobenzene, nitromethane and acetonitrile were dehydrated by keeping over molecular sieves for 48 hrs. and were finally distilled at the appropriate temperatures. Formic acid (Riedel) was refluxed with phthalic anhydride for 10-12 hrs. Then it was distilled and the fraction distilling at 100.5° was collected and used. Acids such as fluorosulphuric, chlorosulphuric and disulphuric acids were prepared and purified by the standard methods^{12, 13}.

Antimony trichloride was purified by distillation under reduced pressure. Organic bases were purified by the standard methods. Triphenylphosphine oxide was prepared by the method reported in literature. Pyridine N oxide has been prepared by the method reported by Ochiai¹⁴.

Preparation of the adducts $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{SO}_3$ and $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{SO}_3$:

Sulphur trioxide (1 g) was distilled into a well cooled suspension of antimony trichloride (5 g) in carbon tetrachloride, when a white compound separated out. Excess of the solution of sulphur trioxide was decanted off and the precipitate repeatedly washed with anhydrous carbon tetrachloride. Finally it was dried under vacuum over phosphorus pentoxide. Elemental analysis confirmed the composition of $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{SO}_3$ (Found : Sulphur, 11.08% ; Chlorine, 33.96% ; Required : Sulphur, 10.33% , Chlorine, 34.55%).

When excess sulphur trioxide (7 g) was added to antimony trichloride (5 g) directly at room temperature, a vigorous reaction took place. After completely washing off sulphur trioxide with carbon tetrachloride, it was dried under vacuum. The compound analysed had the composition $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{SO}_3$ (Found : Sulphur, 50.86% ; Chlorine, 23.16% ; Required : Sulphur, 51.25% ; Chlorine, 22.75%).

Method of the preparation of the complexes of bases:

A cold solution of the base (4 g) in carbon tetrachloride was added dropwise with constant

shaking to a cold suspension of antimony trichloride (6 g) in 30 mls of carbon tetrachloride. The reactants were allowed to stand for 4 hrs. at room temperature when white compound separated out. These were filtered in a dry atmosphere and the residue repeatedly washed with carbon tetrachloride and finally dried under vacuum. Stoichiometric composition of these compounds has been established by elemental analysis and is reported in Table I.

character. The possibility of the formation of addition compounds between antimony trichloride and these solvents is ruled out by the fact that on removal of the solvents under vacuum or on the addition of carbon tetrachloride or petroleum ether, only antimony trichloride is thrown out of the solution. Though the nature of the ions formed is not certain yet the conductance in these solvents may be attributed to the ions of the type $SbCl_2^+$ (solvent) $_n^-$

TABLE I. ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES OF ANTIMONY TRICHLORIDE WITH ORGANIC TERTIARY BASES

Complex	Colour and melting point (°C)	Molar conductance in acetonitrile (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	Found (%)		Calcd. (%)		
			Cl	Sb	Cl	Sb	
SbCl ₃ .3C ₆ H ₅ NHCl	White	189	64.80	35.91	20.78	36.21	21.18
SbCl ₃ .3C ₆ CCl	White	178	66.98*	20.11	11.08	20.60	11.78
SbCl ₃ .C ₆ H ₅ N	White	221	72.70	33.21	38.75	34.65	39.64
SbCl ₃ .3C ₆ H ₅ N	White	238	60.63	21.97	25.92	22.89	26.17
SbCl ₃ .3C ₆ H ₇ N	Light yellow	168	63.21	28.91	33.26	29.80	34.08
SbCl ₃ .C ₆ H ₇ N	Light yellow	210	66.52	16.53	18.91	17.31	19.79
SbCl ₃ .C ₆ H ₇ N	White	146	88.92*	32.31	37.01	33.14	37.90
SbCl ₃ .3C ₆ H ₇ N	White	123	81.80*	20.08	23.33	20.99	24.01
SbCl ₃ .C ₆ H ₅ NO	Dirty white	201	78.62*	32.01	39.98	32.94	37.67
SbCl ₃ .3C ₆ H ₅ NO	Dirty white	163	71.70*	19.97	22.19	20.74	23.72
SbCl ₃ .Ph ₃ PO	White	116	73.24*	20.83	23.74	21.45	24.53
SbCl ₃ .3Ph ₃ PO	White	132	70.86*	9.41	10.16	10.30	11.79

* In nitromethane

Electrical conductances were measured in a cell of cell constant 0.39 cm⁻¹ using Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge Type CL01/01A Sr. No. 448. Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded on a double grating infrared spectrophotometer Perkin-Elmer No. 337 and 621. Spectra were recorded in silver chloride optics as nujol mulls. Potassium bromide pellets were also used in certain cases.

Results and Discussion :

Phosphorus pentachloride forms an adduct of composition 2PCl₅.4SbCl₃ with antimony trichloride which has been formulated as $PCl_4^+ PCl_6^- . 4SbCl_3$.¹⁵ Similarly a compound of unusual composition 5CsCl.3SbCl₅ is reported¹⁶. These compounds of unusual stoichiometric composition have necessitated the re-investigation of the complexes of antimony trichloride with acceptor and donor molecules. Antimony trichloride is soluble in nitrobenzene, nitromethane, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide, acetone, acetic and formic acids. Molar conductance values of the millimolar solutions in these solvents are comparable to the values reported for 1:1 electrolytes in these solvents¹⁷ suggesting its ionic

Cl⁻ (solvent) $_n^-$, $SbCl_2^+$ (solvent) $_n^-$ etc. Molecular weight determination in nitrobenzene suggests that it is fairly dissociated in it.

Paul and his coworkers^{18, 19} have suggested a method by which it is possible to indicate whether a particular solute has ionizable chloride ion or not. It involves the study of its behaviour in disulphuric acid where chloride ions are quantitatively converted to chlorosulphuric acid²⁰ as :

Antimony trichloride has a limited solubility in disulphuric acid. Solutions upto 0.1 molality could be obtained. Further addition of antimony trichloride resulted in the separation of white precipitate. Because of the high viscosity of the solvent, it could not be characterised. However conductance and cryoscopic studies in dilute solutions indicate the reaction as :

Cryoscopic titrations against sulphur trioxide²¹ show that two moles of sulphuric acid are produced per mole of antimony trichloride and support the above

mode of the reaction. It, however, gets solvolysed in both fluorosulphuric and chlorosulphuric acids to form the species $\text{Sb}(\text{SO}_3\text{X})_3$. Thus from the above studies, it is evident that there is no indication of the formation of the cations of the type SbO^+ , Sb^{3+} etc. in these media.

Antimony trichloride forms two compounds of composition $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{SO}_3$ and $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{SO}_3$ with sulphur trioxide. Sulphur trioxide does not accept the lone pair of electrons of antimony but combines with one of the chlorine atoms to form chlorosulphate. This is supported by i. r. spectral studies which show important bands at 1270, 1156, 1070, 775, 580, and 540 cm^{-1} corresponding to chlorosulphate ions²⁴. There is a splitting in most of these bands suggesting that there is a distortion in the symmetry which may be due to the polymeric nature of the adducts. This indicates that the compounds are antimony dichloridemonochlorosulphate and antimony trichlorosulphate.

Antimony dichloromonochlorosulphate has low solubility in chlorosulphuric acid. Its conductance shows that it behaves as a weak electrolyte in it. The low conductance of antimony dichloridemonochlorosulphate in chlorosulphuric acid may be due its polymeric nature. Such chlorosulphate bridges has already been reported in the literature^{25, 26}. Since the compounds are fairly soluble in chlorosulphuric acid, the length of the chain may not be very long. Antimony trichlorosulphate is insoluble in various aprotic solvents and also in disulphuric acid. However in chlorosulphuric acid it behaves as a very weak acid as when potassium chlorosulphate is added to its solution, there is a slight decrease in the conductance of the solution due to the removal of the SO_3Cl^- ions²⁷ as :

In order to further understand the nature of antimony trichloride complexes of antimony trichloride with pyridine hydrochloride ($\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot 3(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NH})\text{Cl}$) and triphenylchloromethane ($\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot 3(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{CCl}$) have been isolated in carbon tetrachloride. Compounds of these compositions have been obtained when the base has been used in excess. These high melting complexes are moisture sensitive and fume in moist air. Molar conductance values in nitromethane and dimethylformamide suggest it to be a ionic compound. U. V. spectrum of the

compound shows the presence of ${}_3\text{C}^+$ ion in the solution. Molar extinction coefficient values of the $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{C}^+$ ion shows²⁸ that the ions present in the solution are :

Similar ions can be formulated for the complex $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot 3(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NH})\text{Cl}$. The absorption bands present at 620, 1520, 1400, 1360, 1260, 1200, 1060, 1010, 930, 855 and 760 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the complex $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NHCl}$ are assigned to the pyridinium ions which are at the same positions as has been observed by the earlier workers²⁹⁻³¹. It is noteworthy that in the presence of excess of chloride ion donor molecule, antimony has a tendency to increase its co-ordination number to six to form hexa chloroantimonate ion.

Antimony trichloride also forms complexes with strong donor molecules such as pyridine, quinoline, -picoline, pyridine N-oxide and triphenylphosphine oxide. Organic tertiary bases form compounds of stoichiometric composition $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{B}$ when the components are mixed in 1 : 1 ratio but when the bases are mixed in excess, compounds of composition $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{B}$ are obtained. All these compounds are moisture sensitive. Stoichiometric composition of these complexes has been confirmed by the elemental analysis and is reported in Table 1. These compounds are slightly soluble in nitromethane and acetonitrile. Molar conductance values of the millimolar solutions suggest them to be ionic in nature. Infrared data of these complexes provide further support to the ionic nature of these complexes. Though the infrared spectra of all these complexes have been examined, the spectrum of only pyridine complexes $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ and $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ is being discussed here. In these complexes nitrogen atom of the organic tertiary base is the donor while the antimony atom acts as the acceptor. There are large perturbations in the spectral bands of the components on complex formation. The absorption bands due to pyridine undergo changes similar to those which occur on the formation of the complexes of pyridine of the type $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NHCl}$ ³⁰, CH_3COCl , $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}$ ³⁰, $\text{SeCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ ³² and $\text{TeCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ ³³. The bands at 1620, 1520, 1480, 1360, 1265, 1060 and 770 cm^{-1} are all due to pyridinium ion suggesting that pyridine in these complexes is present as pyridinium

ion. The N-Cl band which is usually present at 650 cm^{-1} is absent in these complexes suggesting that the addition has not taken place at the chlorine atom of antimony trichloride.

There are two absorption bands due to Sb-Cl stretching vibrations at 428 and 256 cm^{-1} in far i. r. spectrum of antimony trichloride. Only one strong absorption band at 376 cm^{-1} could be observed in the present complex. The lowering of Sb-Cl stretching frequency on complex formation with tertiary bases indicates that addition has taken place at the antimony atom. A similar behaviour is exhibited by metal chlorides where M-Cl frequency is lowered on complex formation with donor molecules^{8,4}. Two absorption bands at 640 and 370 cm^{-1} attributed to Oh symmetry around the central metal atom are found at 580 and 340 cm^{-1} due to metal-chlorine band^{8,5}.

Antimony trichloride also forms complexes with strong donor molecules such as triphenylphosphine oxide and pyridine N-oxide. Pyridine N-oxide which is more basic than pyridine forms a white compound of composition $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NO}$. It is insoluble in most of the conventional organic solvents and therefore no physical measurements could be carried out. But infrared spectral studies of the compound show that the absorption bands due to N-O stretching frequencies which are originally present at 1252 , 837 and 544 cm^{-1} are lowered to 1200 , 820 and 530 cm^{-1} suggesting that on complex formation N-O stretching frequency is considerably lowered. A new absorption band at 516 cm^{-1} assigned to M-O stretching frequency confirms the formation of metal-oxygen bond. A splitting of the M-O stretching frequency indicates the distortion of the symmetry around antimony trichloride. Similarly in the spectrum of the adduct of antimony trichloride with triphenylphosphine oxide, there is a lowering of the P-O stretching frequency and the presence of a new metal oxygen bond. It is interesting to note that on complex formation there is a nominal decrease in the P-O stretching frequency. It may be attributed to the back donation of the p-electrons of oxygen to d-orbitals of phosphorus. It overcomes the effect of enhanced P-O bonding and metal-oxygen interaction which would increase the bond order and hence the strength of phosphoryl stretching frequency.

Therefore overall effect is slight decrease of P-O bond frequency.

From all these observations, it may be concluded that antimony trichloride behaves as a fairly strong electrolyte in various aprotic solvents. It gets solvolysed in highly acidic media. In the presence of strong chloride ion acceptor molecules it forms SbCl_6^+ . It has a strong tendency to increase its co-ordination number to six.

References

1. W. R. Troost, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1954, 32, 356.
2. L. H. Anderson and I. Lindquist, *Acta. Chem. Scand.* 1955, 9, 79.
3. V. Gutmann, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1951, 266, 331.
4. G. Jander and K. H. Swart, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1959, 302, 155.
5. A. G. Davies and E. C. Baughan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 1711.
6. M. A. Bredig, H. A. Levy, F. J. Koneshea and D. Cubicciotti, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, 64, 1961.
7. G. Jander and K. H. Swart, *Z. anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1959, 299, 252.
8. G. Jander and K. H. Swart, *Z. anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1959, 301, 54.
9. Gmelin, "Handbuck der anorganischen chemie", 1949, Part 18B.
10. J. R. Lacher, D. E. Campion and J. D. Park, *Science*, 1949, 110, 300.
11. G. B. Porter and E. C. Baughan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 744, 51.
12. J. Mayer and G. Schramm, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, 206, 24.
13. R. J. Gillespie and K. C. Malhotra, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1967 (A), 1994.
14. E. Ochiai, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, 18, 534.
15. L. Kolditz, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1957a, 118, 289.
16. S. B. Stepina, G. V. Zimina and V. E. Plyushcher, *Redk. Shelochnye, Elem. Sb. Doke. Vses. Soveshch.*, 2nd Novosibirsk, 1964, 159.
17. D. A. Couch, P. S. Elmes, J. E. Ferguson, M. L. Greenfield and C. J. Willkins, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1967(A), 1813.
18. R. C. Paul, V. P. Kapila and K. C. Malhotra, *Chem. Commu.*, 1968, 644.
19. R. C. Paul, V. P. Kapila and K. C. Malhotra, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1970 (A), 2267.
20. R. J. Gillespie and K. C. Malhotra, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968 (A), 1934.
21. J. R. Brayford and P. A. H. Wyatt, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1964, 57, 1281.
22. E. A. Robinson and J. A. Ciruna, *Canad J. Chem.*, 1968, 46, 1719.

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23. R. C. Paul, K. K. Paul and K. C. Malhotra, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 717.
24. T. C. Waddington and F. Klanberg, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960(A), 2339.
25. H. A. Lehmann and L. Riesel, *Z. anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1959, 371, 274.
26. R. C. Paul, C. L. Arora and K. C. Malhotra, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 473.
27. R. C. Paul, S. K. Vashisht, K. C. Malhotra and S. S. Pahil, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 21B, 528.
28. V. Gold and B. W. H. Hawes, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 2102.
29. N. N. Greenwood and K. Wade, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 1671.
30. R. C. Paul and S. L. Chadha, *Spectrochim Acta.*, 1966, 22, 615.
31. R. C. Paul, K. K. Paul and K. C. Malhotra, *Chemistry and Industry*, 1968, 1227.
32. A. W. Cordes and T. V. Hughes, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 1640.
33. R. C. Paul, K. K. Paul and K. C. Malhotra, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1969, 22, 847.
34. R. J. Gillespie and A. Whitla, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1969, 47, 4153.
35. D. Cook, S. J. Kuhn and G. A. Olah, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1960, 33, 1669